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Савка Віталій Янович

кандидат політичних наук, доцент кафедри міжнародної політики
ДВНЗ «Ужгородський національний університет», Україна

Vitalii Savka

Candidate of Political Sciences

Associate Professor of the Department of International Politics

Uzhhorod National University, Ukraine

vitalii.savka@uzhnu.edu.ua

ORCID: 0000-0002-4900-2125

FUNCTIONALIST APPROACHES TO INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN INTEGRATION

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Abstract. *The article analyzes functionalism as one of the key theoretical concepts for understanding global and European integration processes. Particular attention is paid to the historical origins and theoretical foundations of functionalism, which emerged as a response to the crisis of the nation-state system and the limitations of the Westphalian model of international relations after the First World War. The study examines the intellectual roots of functionalism in Enlightenment and early liberal thought and outlines its development as an integration theory in the twentieth century. The article focuses on the functionalist approach developed by David Mitrany, emphasizing its core principles, such as the primacy of non-political and technical cooperation, the gradual transfer of functions from the national to the international level, and the concept of ramification as a mechanism for expanding integration across different sectors. Functionalism is presented as an alternative to both federalist and power-based approaches to international organization, prioritizing problem-solving, expert governance, and practical cooperation over formal political authority. Special attention is given to the role of international functional organizations and technocratic networks in weakening national sovereignty through the effective performance of socio-economic functions. The article also addresses key critiques of functionalism, including realist and federalist objections, and assesses its influence on later integration theories, particularly neofunctionalism. It is concluded that although functionalism has limited direct influence on contemporary European Union decision-making, its theoretical legacy remains essential for understanding the dynamics, logic, and non-political foundations of European integration.*

Keywords: *functionalism; European integration; international integration; David Mitrany; sovereignty; international organizations; ramification; neofunctionalism.*

ФУНКЦІОНАЛІСТСЬКІ ПІДХОДИ ДО МІЖНАРОДНОЇ ТА ЄВРОПЕЙСЬКОЇ ІНТЕГРАЦІЇ

Анотація. У статті здійснено ґрунтовний теоретичний аналіз функціоналізму як однієї з ключових концепцій осмислення світових та європейських інтеграційних процесів. Особливу увагу приділено історичним передумовам виникнення функціоналістського підходу, які були зумовлені кризою національно-державної системи та обмеженістю Вестфальської моделі міжнародних відносин після Першої світової війни. Показано, що функціоналізм сформувався як альтернатива політико-силовим і федералістським моделям інтеграції, пропонуючи іншу логіку побудови міжнародного порядку, засновану на практичній співпраці та задоволенні конкретних соціально-економічних потреб.

У статті простежено інтелектуальні витоки функціоналізму в ідеях мислителів доби Просвітництва та раннього лібералізму, а також проаналізовано еволюцію цієї теорії у ХХ столітті. Центральне місце в дослідженні посідає концепція функціоналізму Девіда Мітрані, зокрема її базові принципи: пріоритет неполітичних і технічних сфер співробітництва, поступове перенесення функцій з національного на міжнародний рівень, а також механізм «розгалуження» як рушій інтеграційної динаміки. Обґрунтовано, що ефективна співпраця в окремих секторах створює об'єктивні передумови для поширення інтеграції на інші сфери діяльності, формуючи стійкі транснаціональні взаємозалежності.

Показано, що у функціоналістській теорії суверенітет розглядається не як статична категорія, а як змінний і поступово трансформований феномен, який втрачає свою виключність унаслідок передачі окремих життєво важливих функцій міжнародним інституціям. Наголошено на ролі міжнародних функціональних організацій та технократичних мереж, які, завдяки експертному управлінню та орієнтації на ефективність, здатні послаблювати конфліктний потенціал між державами.

Окремо розглянуто основні критичні зауваження щодо функціоналізму з боку реалістичних і федералістських підходів, зокрема щодо недооцінки політичної влади та проблем демократичної легітимності. Водночас доведено, що попри обмежений безпосередній вплив на сучасний механізм ухвалення рішень у Європейському Союзі, функціоналізм зберігає важливе теоретичне значення для розуміння логіки, поетапності та неполітичних засад європейської та світової інтеграції.

Ключові слова: функціоналізм; європейська інтеграція; міжнародна інтеграція; Девід Мітрані; суверенітет; міжнародні організації; розгалуження; неофункціоналізм.

Formulation of the problem. The study of global (and, in particular, European) integration processes has been and continues to be undertaken by numerous scholars

in the field of international relations as well as in other disciplines, namely economics, sociology, political science, and others. Undoubtedly, integration as a phenomenon is complex and comprehensive; its development is determined by a large number of factors, both internal and external. Its manifestations are multifaceted and have enormous significance for the system as a whole. Therefore, as integration processes evolved, researchers developed theories, concepts, and models that simplify the understanding of those processes expressed in the formation and evolution of the European Union, identify the determining factors of its development, and make it possible to forecast, with greater or lesser accuracy, the future of European integration, as well as to propose specific development strategies.

The theoretical foundations of integration as a process of mutual rapprochement of states aimed at creating a relatively coordinated community began to form in Western Europe after the First World War, which led to disappointment in the international order manifested in the existence of nation-states and the so-called Westphalian system, based on the unconditional priority of national sovereignty. Scholarly schools emerged that sought to logically substantiate the inevitability of the decline of nation-states and the necessity of a new European and global order, and to propose the most rational way of establishing such an international order in which wars would be excluded from social life.

In this context, federalism and functionalism should be highlighted. Proponents of federalism were guided by the belief that a federal system with central and local levels of authority is ideal for Western European states. Functionalism, however, is based on entirely different principles. Its supporters did not seek an ideal form of international community but instead proposed identifying the functions it should perform. Society, they argued, must rationally comprehend its needs and create institutions capable of fulfilling the functions assigned to them.

The analysis of theoretical development models makes it possible to forecast both the integration dynamics themselves and the final outcome of the integration process, which has a significant impact on the development of the international relations system as a whole. Knowledge of theoretical foundations enables the assessment and analysis of each subsequent step.

The methodological basis of the study is the principle of unity and integrity of existence as a universal system that develops, the interconnection of objects and phenomena, the materiality and cognizability of the world, and the continuity and permanence of dialectical development. The basic principles of the research are objectivity and historicism.

The research employs a systemic approach as well as methods of historical cognition: the synchronic method, which considers phenomena in the context of historical circumstances, and the chronological method, which involves the sequential examination of events over time. In addition, the methods of analysis and synthesis are applied.

The purposes of the article. The purpose of the article is to analyze the main provisions of the concept of functionalism with regard to understanding the essence and objectives of global and European integration processes.

The main material presentation. The theory of functionalism underwent a relatively long period of theoretical formation, extending back to the era of late Enlightenment and early liberalism of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries [2, p. 24]. Its basic theoretical point of departure is the classical idealist paradigm, which over time evolved into a number of theories often referred to as transnational theories. One of these is so-called economic transnationalism, which includes several theoretical approaches, among them functionalism and neofunctionalism [3, p. 553].

The earliest signs of the functionalist approach can be found in the works of the French Enlightenment thinker and utopian socialist Claude Saint-Simon, the positivist Auguste Comte, and English liberals Jeremy Bentham and John Stuart Mill. One of the fundamental sources of functionalism is Adam Smith's idea that a country's level of prosperity increases with the growing division of labor, and that the division of labor expands with the enlargement of markets; therefore, all countries should be interested in deepening international cooperation and creating a global world market.

The development of functionalism as an integration theory took place in the twentieth century. The emergence and development of the first, insufficiently successful international organizations, particularly the League of Nations, which was intended to prevent the violent resolution of conflicts, stimulated interest in searching

for viable future alternatives capable of replacing the existing anarchic system based on unlimited national sovereignty.

The League of Nations, as a universal organization for ensuring global peace, attempted to establish rigid legal frameworks within which, through legal instruments in the form of norms and procedures, the necessary structures and mechanisms for resolving international conflicts without the use of military force would be created. During the interwar period and with the outbreak of the Second World War, the entire spectrum of idealist understanding of this method of organizing international relations became apparent.

The lack of legitimacy of the League of Nations (the United States remained outside the organization from the outset; the USSR and Germany joined later; Japan, Italy, and Germany withdrew in the 1930s), its inability to prevent military aggression by its own members (Italy against Ethiopia, Japan against Manchuria), and the outbreak of the Second World War confronted politicians with a crucial question: how to avoid repeating the same mistakes in the future and how to create a truly effective international organization whose members would voluntarily renounce the military resolution of conflicts.

Functionalism was one of the theories that attempted to find a new way to solve the problem of global integration. The founders and proponents of functionalism realized that the sovereignty of many isolated states constituted a major obstacle to universal peace; however, since national policies and national interests remained decisive, they argued that at the initial stage of integration the idea of weakening national sovereignty should be set aside. Instead of addressing issues sensitive to states in terms of sovereignty—such as common foreign or security policy—functionalists focused on developing international cooperation in areas that would be non-conflictual for member states and, at the same time, would promote cooperation among people from different countries in solving concrete problems.

Ultimately, functionalist theory aims to ensure peace through global integration in areas that lie largely outside politics. Therefore, functionalism concentrates on the emergence of international organizations primarily oriented toward economic or technical cooperation.

The intellectual founder of functionalism is considered to be David Mitrany (1888–1975), who was inspired by the work of the British liberal economist Norman Angell *The Great Illusion*, according to which mutual economic interdependence among states renders war irrational. Mitrany's understanding of functionalism was grounded precisely in this idea.

In formulating the main principles and postulates of his functionalist theory, Mitrany was strongly influenced by the activities of various international functional organizations of the late nineteenth century, such as the International Telegraph Union (1865) and the Universal Postal Union (1865). According to Mitrany, these organizations consistently and effectively served the interests of the world as a whole rather than those of individual states [6, pp. 89–90].

The works *The Progress of International Government* [6] and especially *A Working Peace System* [4] are considered classical functionalist texts. Mitrany continued to publish actively until his death in 1975, when his final scholarly monograph, *The Functional Theory of Politics*, which synthesized his earlier works, was published [5].

Following the Second World War, functionalism experienced significant development. A number of Mitrany's followers examined various international functional structures within the United Nations, while within the European integration process particular attention was paid to the European Coal and Steel Community. The main representatives of this theoretical current included first-generation functionalists such as Harry Mance and L. White, while the next generation was represented primarily by the works of Patrick Sewell [7] and Paul Taylor [8].

Mitrany advocated the idea of creating a new type of international association—an association of states that would retain their identity and continue to pursue independent policies. Such an association was to be based on the emergence of a kind of community among individual actors (states), with the functional approach serving as the key condition for its operation.

Mitrany's primary objective was the elimination of the anarchically organized international system and its replacement with a functioning world system. He emphasized that “peace cannot be secured if we organize society by means of what

divides it” [4, p. 68]. He understood that this would be a long-term process accompanied by many small steps. The main problem of a functioning world system, in his view, lay in the gradual transfer of sovereignty from the national to the international level.

As long as an international institution receives from its members a concrete task (function) along with permanent powers and instruments, it is necessary to gradually withdraw part of the national sovereignty of member states. With an increasing number of such tasks, the international organization acquires more sovereignty at the expense of national sovereignty. Thus, according to Mitrany, vital socio-economic functions of the state should be transferred to the competence of a world organization that would demonstrate its ability to perform these functions more effectively than the nation-state.

Through its activities in various non-political spheres, such a functionalist organization weakens the sovereignty of nation-states. Citizens conclude a social contract not only with their national state but also with a supranational institution capable of satisfying their vital needs just as effectively, or even more effectively [1, p. 38]. “A new world authority emerges through agreements rather than conquest, and its status will depend on the extent to which sovereignty is distanced from national groups” [4, p. 128].

Internationally supported cooperation among people from different countries in addressing concrete social, cultural, educational, migration, and other problems has a highly positive psychological effect, as it eliminates persistent stereotypes in the perception of representatives of other nations and states. Furthermore, the logical continuation of such cooperation is the creation of new interconnections which, together with the functional reorganization of the international community, lead to the gradual emergence of a supranational community.

Successful cooperation among political representatives of states in various public spheres and their understanding of the diverse positions of their partners also has a positive impact on resolving other issues that, under different conditions, might be regarded as acute conflicts.

The main prerequisite for solving international problems is functional cooperation carried out by organizations based on principles fundamentally different from those of

power and sovereignty. Functionalists point to such areas as economics, trade, culture, communications, tourism, and education—fields in which international institutions could operate without constant clashes with national interests.

Mitrany deliberately paid little attention to political intergovernmental organizations, as issues of power were secondary for him. In his view, functionalism recognizes only one logic—the logic of the problem. Functional action implies constant adaptation to changing goals and conditions. He argued that practical cooperation is more important than the formal subordination of a minority to the will of a majority. [4, c. 130]

Mitrany supported the idea of creating functionalist international organizations governed by specialized agencies headed by experts whose conclusions would be decisive in specific areas, while the role of political power in this process was of no importance. Specialized UN agencies (such as UNESCO and FAO) were often cited as examples.

He rejected the traditional parliamentary and power-based system of decision-making and instead proposed the so-called “management committee government,” the essence of which lies in the creation of “functional assemblies” composed of specialists who provide professional expertise and recommendations. Their professional knowledge serves as a guarantee of the highest efficiency of decisions. [1, c. 39]

Mitrany complemented this idea with the principle that no one should share power without simultaneously sharing responsibility. Functional structures should be created by individuals who perform specific functions [5, c. 119], and under the condition of “functional assemblies,” expert decisions would be directly linked to responsibility. Formal representative status, he argued, also entails a certain degree of democratic accountability.

According to Mitrany, international technocratic networks should be created without the participation of politicians, permeating all areas of state activity. These organizations should focus exclusively on technical and non-political problems, a point Mitrany consistently emphasized.

A key mechanism in the dynamics of functional integration, according to Mitrany, is the so-called *ramification*. Successful cooperation in one technical field can

stimulate cooperation in others. This process operates through two main mechanisms: first, positive experiences of cooperation encourage public opinion to demand expansion into other areas; second, such cooperation creates objective preconditions for further collaboration. Through ramification, states become increasingly interconnected across multiple functional spheres and thus lose interest in disrupting these ties, even in the event of serious conflicts that might otherwise lead to war.

Mitrany associated the concept of “functional” not only with “non-political” but also with “non-controversial.” National sovereignty is gradually and almost imperceptibly reduced and replaced by a new network of relations in which state borders lose their significance. The result of this long process of sovereignty transfer, according to Mitrany, should be the creation of a world society. Unlike his predecessors, he assigned a decisive role to sectoral integration that gradually “spills over” from one sphere into another.

However, Mitrany did not advocate the creation of a federal order as the ultimate goal of functionalism, believing that political federations would soon replicate the mistakes of the nation-state, albeit at a higher level. [2, c. 24] He regarded the idea of a world federation as utopian and unfeasible in reality. Existing federal states, such as Germany or Switzerland, he viewed as national federations based on historical affinities, whose experience cannot be artificially transferred to the international level characterized by greater diversity and complexity. Moreover, he believed that a federalized community would be unable to resolve complex economic and social problems.

Mitrany and his followers were generally skeptical of regional integration, as the formation of localized structures involving only a few states would undermine the emergence of a global system. In his view, functional regions are not geographical units, such as Western Europe, but practical sectors such as rail transport, aviation, or epidemiological control. [4, c. 111-116]

According to classical functionalist theory, a working world system is possible only on a global basis, not within a regional community. Mitrany regarded European integration as an attempt to build a closed, exclusive system aimed at federating Europe, which would not be inclined to resolve global problems through a functionalist

approach. He also believed that regionalism could give rise to a new form of nationalism by necessitating a clear distinction between “us” and “others.” [2, c. 27-28]

Throughout its existence, functionalism has also faced considerable criticism. Hans Morgenthau sharply criticized the functionalist neglect of political borders, considering it naive to assume that nation-states would eventually lose citizens’ support in favor of supranational entities. [2, c. 28] Another line of criticism came from federalists, who viewed “technocratic power” as undemocratic. [7, c. 42]

Functionalism, particularly its most prominent methodological tool—ramification—has influenced a wide range of scholars studying European integration. It has significantly shaped post-war liberal thought and has been reflected in numerous European integration theories and approaches, especially those emphasizing the idea of “rational supranationality.” Traces of classical functionalism can also be found in world federalism, transactionalism, and, most notably, in neofunctionalism and the so-called new neofunctionalism.

Functionalism rejected the federalist thesis of the inevitability of a European constitutional process and a clear division between functional and political authority. Instead, it focused on vital problems that cannot be resolved by the efforts of a single authority alone.

Although functionalism no longer has significant influence on EU decision-making, knowledge of its theoretical foundations remains essential for understanding the overall dynamics of European integration, particularly its conceptual underpinnings. Functionalism became one of the concepts of European integration strategy, emphasizing the practical and non-political nature of integration based on the gradual expansion of cooperation from one sphere of activity to another.

Conclusions. The article demonstrates that functionalism constitutes an important theoretical approach to understanding global and European integration processes, offering an alternative to power-based and federalist models of international order. By emphasizing non-political and technical cooperation, functionalism highlights the role of practical problem-solving, expertise, and sectoral interaction in reducing conflict and fostering stable forms of international cooperation. Central to this approach is the

concept of ramification, which explains the gradual expansion of integration through the successful performance of specific functions across interconnected spheres.

At the same time, the study shows that functionalism conceptualizes sovereignty as a dynamic and evolving phenomenon, gradually transformed through the transfer of functions rather than through abrupt political integration. Although the theory has been criticized for underestimating political power and democratic accountability, its intellectual legacy has significantly influenced later integration theories, particularly neofunctionalism. Consequently, functionalism retains lasting analytical value for understanding the incremental, non-political, and functional foundations of European and international integration.

References

1. Chryssochoou D. *Theorizing European Integration*. London, 2001. 240 p.
2. Eilstrup-Sangiovanni M. *Interwar and Postwar Ideas of Europe. Debates on European Integration. A Reader*. Ed. Eilstrup-Sangiovanni, Mette. Houndmills, Basingstoke, 2006.
3. Krejčí O. *Mezinárodní politika*. Praha, 2001. 672 p.
4. Mitrany D. *A Working Peace System: An Argument for the Functional Development of International Organization*. Reprinted in Taylor P. and Groom A. J. R. (eds.). *The Functional Theory of Politics*. London, 1975. *O'Neal M. Theories of integrations*. N.-Y., 1992. 426 p.
5. Mitrany D. *The Functional Theory of Politics*. London, 1975. 319 p.
6. Mitrany D. *The Progress of International Government*. New Haven, 1982. 585 p.
7. Sewell P. *Functionalism and World Politics*. London. 1986. 417 p.
8. Taylor P. *Functionalism and Strategies for International Integration*. *Groom A. J. R., Taylor P. (eds.). Functionalism. Theory and Practice in International Relations*. London, 1975. 354 p.